

FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN CLASSES. WITH GREAT FILLING

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Annotation: An article about the problems of teaching in large classes is considered to be difficult to teach in large classes. There are, of course, objective difficulties, but there are also methods that can help with this. Experience shows that large classes can be taught effectively.

Key words: large occupancy, objective difficulties, methods, experience shows, large classrooms, can be taught effectively, foreign language teaching, negatively, classroom size.

Аннотация: Статья о проблемах обучения в классах с большой наполняемостью считается, что преподавать в больших классах сложно. Существуют, конечно, и объективные трудности, но есть и методы, которые могут в этом помочь. Опыт показывает, что в больших классах можно преподавать эффективно.

Ключевые слова: большой наполняемостью, объективные трудности, методы, опыт показывает, больших классах, можно преподавать эффективно, обучения иностранному языку, негативно, размера классного помещения.

It is believed that teaching in large classes is difficult. However, such classes also involve many opportunities for learning a foreign language. "Big" for learning. A foreign language class is considered to be a group of more than twelve people. Foreign teachers, native speakers, teaching in other countries, often face classes with 50 or more students. As a result of this, strategies and methods have appeared that allow the teacher to help in such situations.

Problems of learning in the classroom with high filling capacity.

Teachers have a negative attitude towards teaching a foreign language in a class with a large number of students, often because of the size of the classroom. There are, of course, objective difficulties, but there are also methods that can help with this. Experience shows that large classes can be taught effectively.

We note the main problems.

Large Class Teaching Strategies

Discomfort. Joint work of students is difficult due to the lack of free space.

In traditional classrooms, desks are often arranged in rows with the teacher's desk in the center in front of the blackboard. This is more suitable for lecturing, and not for teaching a foreign language. It is important to optimize the organization of furniture in a limited space.

- Move the desks in groups. This allows students to see the board, see each other, communicate and move around.

- Place the teacher's desk (if needed at all) at the edge of the board so that the view is not obstructed.

- Consider how to group students, create mixed groups: boys-girls, children of different academic levels. Divide into different groups of children who can potentially interfere with each other's work.

- For visual aids, use the walls (including the ceiling). Create an engaging environment that will help motivate students.

Make posters, tables, pictures that can be hung in the classroom and used in subsequent lessons to refer back to when reviewing.

- If possible, use a different space (corridor, adjoining classrooms), sometimes a change of scenery can also help motivate children and allow for games that require more space.

Control. It is difficult to control discipline in the classroom and ensure that all students work on the task at hand, impossible. Children may be too noisy when working in a group. If some students are not interested or they are not set to work, they interfere with the rest. There are other distractions that interfere with concentration, but student misbehavior can go unnoticed. It is also difficult to ensure that all children use a foreign language, since they often switch to their native language when completing a task. It often happens that a teacher, teaching in classes with a large occupancy, tries to ensure tight control of the learning process. Excessive control creates stress for the teacher and has a negative impact on students. Sometimes it is necessary to "retreat" a little, to strive for a softer atmosphere. The students have to communicate and that means the classroom will be noisy, but that noise is productive.

Ways to solve the problem of control:

- Installation for execution. Explain to the class at the beginning of the lesson that they will achieve more if they work together. Tell the children what they will need to do by briefly mentioning each step. It is also useful to talk about the purpose of this lesson. For example, "by the end of this activity, you will be able to describe the rooms in your house in English." This helps to focus on the task at hand.

- Clarity of tasks. Ensure that the goal is achievable, results visible, and time to complete. All assignments must have an end result or product that can be measured. A task without a measurable result leads to confusion and lack of control. Also, try to include tasks that require the use of a foreign language and cannot be completed using the native language.

- Noise control. Do not raise your voice to get the attention of the class. Come up with a sign that is used to calm the class (for example, clapping your hands). Often a whisper rather than a shout can be more effective in trying to establish silence. Use a signal (raising your hand) when you need to say something.

- Responsibility of students. Introduce the children to their roles. Create a duty schedule (wipe off the board, collect work, etc.). It is especially important to give separate tasks to weaker students.

- Collective work. Use tasks that involve group interaction. It is much easier to supervise four groups of five students than one big one. Appoint a leader in each group who is responsible for making sure everyone has a say in the work. Some teachers use armbands or another symbol to represent the leader of the group.

- Control of the use of a foreign language. Instead of pair work, use work in triplets, where the third student makes sure that the other two do not switch to Russian. Language observers may be appointed in groups of any size. Students switch roles from task to task.

It is good to prevent the use of the native language and instead of a foreign language, apply a penalty "red card". The card is given to the one who violated the rule. The one who is left with a penalty card at the end of the lesson performs additional tasks.

- Competition. Competition between groups can be held with a scoring or points system awarded after each task. You can divide the class into groups for an entire quarter and award points at the end of each topic. Personal attention. In a large class, it is impossible to help all students and give enough attention to each. Weaker students feel insecure, not knowing how to complete the task.

- Use of student names. At the first lesson, it is difficult, but very important, to remember and use the names of the children. Come up with ways to help remember a large number of names: business cards, labels, name games, etc. The use of names in a large class has a big effect on an unfamiliar teacher.

- Control and feedback. Not all children require feedback in every lesson. Supervise groups during assignments and only offer help when needed. Let the commanders of the groups or those who observe the use of a foreign language report the presence of problems and how the task is being carried out.

- Support system. Students should work together from time to time. The teacher can distribute who will work with whom. In this way, stronger students may be paired with weaker children who need help. The child interacts with his partner at a certain stage of the lesson, this happens most effectively when you need to check what the children have learned at the end of each topic, each stage. Students can also check each other's work.

- Teacher's notes. When monitoring, make notes in your notebook, write down everything that could be useful for class work. Feedback should always serve progress, that is, first tell the child or group what they have already achieved, and then add what needs to be done to keep moving forward.

EVALUATION. It is not possible to check the work of all students, the correct pronunciation. In addition, it lacks the time it takes to evaluate each of them.

- Peer ratings. Research has shown that children value feedback from their peers more than from their teachers. Use tasks where individual students or groups can check or add something to the work, mark another. This is best applied as part of the lesson, not as a correction, but rather as an addition to what has been said. This is not rated. Children learn from each other.

- Sample answer. Uses an assignment that has visible results (eg poster, diagram, match, etc.) where groups compare their findings to a sample response. This saves time collecting and checking responses.

- Joint check. If there is work to be checked, use methods where the role of the teacher is minimal. Let the students exchange books, notebooks and check each other's answers under the dictation of the teacher. The children can take turns giving the correct answers while the others check them. You can also use pair checking before the teacher explains the rule, etc.

- Degree of participation. Figure out how to evaluate everyone's contribution to the task. To what extent was a foreign language used, what kind of help was provided by classmates? Explain this type of assessment at the start of class and emphasize that getting a good "participation grade" is up to them.

EFFICIENCY OF LEARNING. . In a large class, it is difficult for the teacher to understand who has learned what, which child needs help, and which one has understood everything that was planned in the lesson. Due to the high level of noise, it is difficult to figure out which stages of the lesson were successful and which did not bring the desired result.

Conclusion: Children do well in large classes, and it must be understood that teaching in high-capacity classrooms can be very effective. The task of the teacher is to change his attitude to the problem. It is necessary to move away

from the behavior of a teacher who stands in the center of the class and “gives knowledge” to children. The initiative must be given to the students. It is much more useful for students to study, analyze, interact using a foreign language when performing tasks themselves.

References:

1. Budagov R.A. language-reality-language. Moscow, 1985.
2. Elizarova G.V. Culture and teaching foreign languages. St. Petersburg, 2005.
3. Ter - Minasova S.G. language and intercultural communication. Moscow, 2000 Links to used resources
4. <http://www.englishclub.com/tefchingtips/teaching-large-classes.htm>
5. The history of the formation and functioning of kinship terms Israilova, Gulnara Mamadzhanovna
6. STATEMENT OF THE LEARNING TASK AS A MEANS OF LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT OF A YOUNGER STUDENT IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS Israilova Gulnara
7. EVALUATIVE VOCABULARY AND MEANS ITS MANIFESTATIONS Gulnara Mamajanovna Israilova 2023 Maqola (Xorijiy jurnal) Israilova G 1.pdf
8. Preparing young people for family life Israilova, Gulnara Mamadjanovna 2022
9. Develop students' ability to work independently using different technologies. Israilova, Gulnara Mamajanova 2022
Turakulova Feruza Aminovna. Qualified practice and media education
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